

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF CUSTOMER FEEDBACK ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INSTAGRAM CONTENT AND BRAND AWARENESS AMONG MILLENIALS AND GEN Z: A REGRESSION ANALYSIS

AISSYA PUTRI ZANUARIZQI¹, IRMAWAN RAHYADI², ANIS FAIQOH NURULLITA³, DIVIA INDIRA ARIFIN⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Communication Department, BINUS Graduate Program-Master of Communication Science, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia

E-mail: ¹aisya.zanuarizqi@binus.ac.id, ²irmawan.rahyadi@binus.edu, ³anis.nurullita@binus.ac.id, ⁴divia.arifin@binus.ac.id

*Corresponding author: aisya.zanuarizqi@binus.ac.id

ABSTRACT

In the digital era, social media plays a vital role as a communication tool where users can share information and connect, with Instagram being one of the platforms. This study aims to determine whether Instagram content (X) directly or indirectly affects brand awareness (Y) through customer feedback (Z) as an intervening variable. The study population consists of Instagram followers of @minisoxsamono_kudus. Sampling was conducted using reliance available sampling through a questionnaire, resulting in 128 respondents. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed using regression and path analysis with SPSS 25 software. The results show that Instagram Content (X) significantly affects Customer Feedback (Z) with a t-value (12.604) > t-table (1.979) and Brand Awareness (Y) with a t-value (11.302) > t-table (1.979). Additionally, Customer Feedback (Z) significantly influences Brand Awareness (Y) with t-value (10.939) > t-table (1.979). Path analysis reveals that the direct effect of $X \rightarrow Y$ is 0.747, while the indirect effect of $X \rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$ is 1.2314. The Sobel test for mediation shows a t-value (8.323) > t-table (1.979), indicating that Instagram Content (X), through Customer Feedback (Z), has a positive and significant impact on Brand Awareness (Y). It is recommended that Miniso X Samono Kudus continue innovating and creatively improving the quality of Instagram content while consistently considering customer feedback to enhance the brand awareness of Miniso X Samono Kudus.

Keywords: *Content Instagram, Customer Feedback, Brand Awareness, Miniso X Samono*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's modern digital era, social media has become one of the leading platforms for marketers to keep up with ever-evolving trends. The effective utilization of social media can significantly enhance brand visibility, foster customer engagement, and expand audience reach. Social media provides real-time information and has a considerable impact on society. Therefore, it is considered more effective, cost-efficient, and targeted. Social media is accessible to people worldwide and enables communication across different countries.

Data from [1] reveals that the three most widely used social media platforms among Indonesians are WhatsApp, used by 90.9% of the population, followed by Instagram at 85.3%, and Facebook at 81.6%. Instagram, which ranks second, offers a variety of attractive features

compared to the other two. Users can stay connected with their loved ones, follow their favourite celebrities, and engage in appealing and aesthetic activities—all conveniently within a single platform.

The advantage of Instagram over other social media platforms lies in its ability to serve as a marketing medium that delivers brand messages through images or one-minute videos, along with its live video feature. A study by Forrester Research highlights Instagram's popularity as a marketing platform surpassing that of Facebook. Additionally, Forbes describes Instagram as a highly effective sales tool [2].

Data from We Are Social in October 2023 reveals that Indonesia has 104.8 million active social media accounts, ranking as the fourth-largest Instagram user base in the world. Globally, We Are Social recorded 1.64 billion Instagram users in

October 2023, reflecting a 2.5% quarterly increase and an impressive 18.1% annual growth [3].

The Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) reported that internet users in Indonesia reached 221,563,479 people in 2024. Since 2018, Indonesia's internet penetration has steadily increased, reaching 64.8% in 2018, 73.7% in 2020, and 77.01% in 2022 [4].

With the high internet penetration in Indonesia, Instagram has become a strategic medium for retail companies to reach consumers effectively. Beyond being a photo-sharing platform, Instagram is now a primary marketing tool through advertisements, collaborations with influencers, and interactive content. This provides retail companies with opportunities to enhance brand awareness and gain direct insights into customer feedback, enabling them to respond to market needs more quickly and effectively.

Instagram is one of the most widely used social media platforms for marketing [5]. Many brands used Instagram because it is the most prominent and preferred social media platform utilized by influencers for sharing brand related content. The effective optimization of Instagram usage is a critical factor in fostering strong relationships with customer enhancing brand awareness.

The Chairman of the Indonesian Retail Companies Association, Roy N. Mandey, stated that as of June 2024, the growth of retail companies had reached 4.7%-4.8% [6]. One of the retail companies leveraging Instagram to enhance brand awareness is Miniso X Samono Kudus. Various strategies are employed, such as creating engaging content. Therefore, this study is titled: "The Mediating Effect Of Customer Feedback On The Relationship Between Instagram Content And Brand Awareness Among Millenials And Gen Z: A Regression Analysis"

2. THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Theory of Planned Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) was popularized by social psychologist Icek Ajzen in 1980 [7], This theory is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which outlines that subjective norms and attitudes toward the behaviour influence the decision to act [8]. The Theory of Planned Behavior is a behavioural theory that identifies individuals' beliefs regarding control over the outcomes of their actions. It emphasizes the role of perceived behavioural control in influencing decision-making and actions. [7].

Figure 1: Theory of Planned Behavior [9]

The Theory of Planned Behavior explains that attitudes toward behaviour are key in predicting a person's actions. However, it is also essential to consider a person's attitude when evaluating subjective norms and measuring the perceived behavioural control they feel.

2.1 Cognitive Dissonance Theory

The Cognitive Dissonance Theory was introduced by Leon Festinger in 1957 to explain the relationship between motivation, perception, and an individual's cognition [10]. This theory explains the condition that motivates individuals to change their opinions, attitudes, beliefs, or behaviours to reduce the discomfort caused by cognitive dissonance. Festinger [10] defined 'cognition' as any individual knows themselves or their environment. Cognitive dissonance theory begins by proposing that cognitive pairs can be relevant or irrelevant to each other. If two cognitions are relevant and interconnected, then consonance occurs.

However, if two cognitions are relevant but contradictory, the presence of dissonance will cause psychological discomfort and motivate the individual to take action to resolve it. The greater the dissonance, the greater the pressure on the individual to reduce that dissonance [11]. The presence of dissonance and the mechanisms humans use to resolve it intrigued Festinger, leading him to further develop the cognitive dissonance theory.

2.2 Social Media Marketing

According to [12], social media marketing is creating and promoting online marketing activities on social media platforms that provide value to stakeholders. Nowadays, businesses need to experiment and adjust to market conditions using social media marketing tactics to achieve company goals [13].

Cited in [14], brand awareness is the brand's strength that enables consumers to remember it [15]. The more consumers a company reaches in a short period, the faster brand awareness spreads [16]. Additionally, brand awareness is a crucial element of

brand equity, directly influencing consumer attitudes and perceptions toward the brand. Sometimes, it may lead consumers to suspend their brand loyalty and choose a different brand [17].

2.3 Content Instagram

According to Ellison [18], social networking sites are web-based services that allow individuals to create public or semi-public profiles within a limited system, which other users can view, connect with others, and view and control connections made within the system.

Instagram content refers to marketing using content published through the Instagram platform to engage the audience. According to [19], content is anything that helps engage users with a product or service, which can be used both on and off the web and across any media, thus expanding its reach.

According to George, content is material used for self-expression and public accessibility, such as writing and art [20]. It includes various formats in new media, such as text, images, audio, and video. Content can be delivered through multiple platforms, both directly and indirectly, including the internet, television, audio CDs, and mobile phones [21].

2.4 Customer Feedback

The book *Marketing: Real People, Real Choices* by [22] explains that customer feedback on social media platforms like Instagram is a crucial indicator of customer satisfaction and loyalty. Feedback measures customer reactions to a post and adjusts content and marketing strategies based on customer responses. Positive and negative feedback provides valuable insights for improving service and product quality.

According to McCarty [23], customer feedback is the term used to describe the information customers provide about their experiences with a product or service. This information helps organizations understand the various products or services that make customers willing to pay for something enjoyable and vital.

Customer feedback from customers can vary. According to [24], customer feedback can drive development and improvement activities for the products or services offered by a company. Feedback can take the form of suggestions or criticism, whether positive or negative. Therefore, to measure customer feedback, feedback related to customer satisfaction with the product and promotional feedback on the product is typically selected. These variables are chosen because both are essential factors for a company's growth [23].

2.5 Brand Awareness

Brand awareness refers to a consumer's ability to recognize or recall a brand based on a specific product category. The more consumers recognize a brand, the higher the level of awareness of that brand, which makes it easier for potential customers to make purchasing decisions regarding that brand [25].

Figure 2: The Brand Awareness Pyramid [26]

The synergy of the brand name, logo design, brand image, and slogan influence brand awareness. According to [27] the level of brand awareness are as follows:

1. Unaware of Brand: This is the lowest level in the brand awareness pyramid, where consumers do not know or recognize the brand's existence. At this stage, the brand has not yet impacted the consumer's awareness, and they are completely unfamiliar with it.
2. Brand Recognition: This level refers to the association or familiarity a consumer has gained from previous exposure to the brand. It influences the consumer's ability to identify and recognize the brand when encountering it again. Brand recognition is typically triggered when a consumer comes across a logo, name, or visual they have seen before and can associate it with a particular product or service.
3. Brand Recall: Brand recall reflects a deeper level of awareness where the brand comes to mind when a consumer is prompted with a specific product category. For example, a brand name may immediately appear when a consumer thinks about a certain type of product, such as soft drinks. This level of awareness indicates a stronger mental connection between the consumer and the brand.
4. Top of Mind: This is the highest level of brand awareness, positioning the brand as the consumer's first and preferred choice in their mind. A brand that achieves top-of-mind awareness becomes the go-to option, often influencing purchasing decisions without the

consumer considering other alternatives. This is a critical stage, as it reflects the brand's dominance in the consumer's memory, especially when making decisions quickly and without going through a detailed selection process.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a positivist paradigm with a quantitative and explanatory approach. Data collection was conducted through a survey method using incidental sampling (Reliance Available Sampling). 132 respondents participated by filling out a questionnaire distributed via Microsoft Forms. However, only 128 responses were deemed valid for analysis after data cleaning. The data used in this study cannot be publicly shared as it contains respondents' personal information. Public disclosure of the data may compromise the privacy and confidentiality of participants, which research ethics principles must safeguard. Therefore, access to the data can only be granted upon approved request and in compliance with applicable ethical guidelines.

The collected data was then analyzed using linear regression and the Sobel test with SPSS 25 to examine the relationships between variables. A 5-point Likert scale was used in the questionnaire, divided into the following levels:

Table 1: Likert Scale

Value	Scale Rating
5	Strongly Agree
4	Agree
3	Neutral
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

To ensure the reliability and validity of the measurement instruments, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability tests were conducted. The hypotheses tested in this study are as follows:

Figure 3: Theoretical Framework

H₁: The influence of Instagram content on customer feedback at Miniso X Samono Kudus.

H₂: The influence of Instagram content on brand awareness at Miniso X Samono Kudus.

H₃: The influence of customer feedback on brand

awareness at Miniso X Samono Kudus.

H₄: The influence of Instagram content on brand awareness through customer feedback at Miniso X Samono Kudus.

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

In this case, descriptive statistics serves solely to describe the state of the sample without generalizing or inferences about the entire population. The discussion of descriptive statistics involves presenting data in frequency distribution tables, graphs, or other formats that do not aim to draw conclusions related to generalizations [28].

3.2 Validity Test

A validity test is the ability to construct indicators used to measure the accuracy level of a questionnaire. This means determining whether the questionnaire created is accurate or not. If the questionnaire is correct, it can be used; however, further testing is required if it is not accurate [29]. The testing process is done by correlating each question item with the total score and then interpreting the resulting correlation coefficient. The resulting correlation coefficient is compared with the r-table value ($df = n - 2$), where n is the number of respondents. The criteria for the validity test are as follows:

1. If r value $>$ r Table, the item is considered valid.
2. If r value $<$ r Table, the item is considered invalid.

3.3 Reliability Test

One commonly used method to measure reliability is Cronbach's Alpha. Reliability refers to the extent to which a measurement tool can be trusted to produce accurate results. A measurement tool is considered reliable if its results are consistent and precise, demonstrating that the tool is dependable and credible [30]. The levels of Cronbach's Alpha are as follows:

Table 2. Levels of Reliability [31]

α Value	Level of Reliability
0.00 – 0.20	Less reliable
>0.20 – 0.40	Slightly reliable
>0.40 – 0.60	Moderately reliable
>0.60 – 0.80	Reliable
>0.80 – 1.00	Highly reliable

3.4 Simple Linear Regression

Simple linear regression is a method to model the linear relationship between a single independent variable (X) and a dependent variable (Y). This analysis can be used to determine the direction of the relationship between the

independent variable and the dependent variable—whether it is positive or negative—and to predict the dependent variable’s value when the independent variable’s value increases or decreases. Typically, simple regression uses data on an interval or ratio scale [32]. The formula for simple linear regression is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon_i$$

Note:

Y: dependen tvariabel

β_0 : constant (*intercept*)

β_1 : regression coefficient (*slope*)

X_1 : independent variable

ε : *error*

3.5 F-Test

According to [33], the F-test aims to assess the feasibility of the research model. It determines whether the regression equation can be used to evaluate the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable. The F-table value is determined at a 5% significance level with degrees of freedom ($df1 = k - 1$ and $df2 = n - k$, where N is the number of respondents, and K is the total number of independent and dependent variables

1. If $F_{calculated} < F_{table}$ and the probability value (*sig. f*) $> \alpha (0,05)$ it can be concluded that the independent variables simultaneously have no significant influence on the dependent variable.
2. If $F_{calculated} > F_{table}$ and the probability value (*sig. f*) $< \alpha (0,05)$ it can be concluded that the independent variables simultaneously have a significant influence on the dependent variable.

3.6 T-Test

The T-test, or Partial Test, is used to evaluate the influence of each independent variable individually on the dependent variable. This test helps determine the significance of each independent variable’s contribution to influencing the dependent variable by isolating the effects of each independent variable one by one [33]. The calculation results will be compared with the r-table value where $df = n - 2$ (*sig. 5%*, where n is the sample size).

According to [34], in making decisions for the T-test, the criteria are as follows:

1. There is an effect or influence if the calculated t-value $>$ t-table value.
2. If the calculated t-value $<$ t-table value, then there is no effect or influence

3.7 Path Analysis (Sobel Test)

Mediation hypothesis testing can be conducted using the procedure developed by Sobel

[35], known as the Sobel Test. The Sobel test is conducted by testing the strength of the indirect effect of X on Y through Z.

$$sab = \sqrt{b^2sa^2 + a^2sb^2 + sa^2sb^2}$$

Note:

Sab: the standard error of the indirect effect

a: the path coefficient from the independent variable (X) to the intervening variable (Z)

b: the path coefficient from the intervening variable (Z) to the dependent variable (Y)

sa: the standard error of the coefficient a

sb: the standard error of the coefficient b

Figure 4. Illustration of mediation [36]

To test the significance of the indirect effect, the t-value of the coefficient ab needs to be calculated using the following formula:

$$t = \frac{ab}{sab}$$

The calculated t-value is compared to the critical t-table. If the calculated t-value $>$ the critical t-table, it can be concluded that there is a significant mediation effect. The Sobel test assumes a large sample size. If the sample size is small, the Sobel test becomes less conservative, which may be less reliable in detecting the true mediation effect. The Sobel Test can also be calculated using a Sobel calculator [37]. The Sobel calculator can be accessed at <https://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Figure 5. Dashboard Respondents (Source: primary data processed using Power BI and Canva)

The dashboard in Figure 5 illustrates the survey completion statistics and demographic

distribution of the respondents. Of 132 participants, 97% completed the survey, with an average completion time of 4 minutes and 55 seconds.

Demographically, most respondents belonged to Generation Z, representing 71% of the 19–25 age group, followed by Millennials in the 26–35 age group at 24%. Regarding gender distribution, females comprised 75% of the respondents, while males accounted for 25%. Regarding educational background, most participants held a D4/S1 degree.

Geographically, the survey was primarily concentrated in Central Java, with Kudus recording the highest number of respondents (56), followed by Jepara (18), Semarang (13), Demak (12), Pati (6), and other cities (23). The distribution map highlights the significant participation from these regions. Given Generation Z's and Millennials' dominance, the survey results provide valuable insights into the respondents' demographic profiles and geographical locations.

4.2 Validity Test

The validity test was conducted using SPSS 25 software. Before performing the test, the r-table value was determined based on:

$$df = n - 2$$

$$df = 128 - 2$$

$$df = 126$$

$$r\ table_{(0.05,126)} = 1,736$$

The results of the validity test using SPSS 25 are as follows:

Table 3. The Result of The Validity Test (Source: primary data processed using SPSS 25)

Variable	Item	r-value	r-table	Result
Content Instagram (X)	X1	0,847	0,1736	Valid
	X2	0,767		Valid
	X3	0,840		Valid
	X4	0,781		Valid
	X5	0,881		Valid
	X6	0,817		Valid
Customer Feedback (Z)	Z1	0,724		Valid
	Z2	0,753		Valid
	Z3	0,771		Valid
	Z4	0,809		Valid
	Z5	0,792		Valid
	Z6	0,770		Valid
	Y1	0,803	Valid	
	Y2	0,831	Valid	

Variable	Item	r-value	r-table	Result
Brand Awareness (Y)	Y3	0,809		Valid
	Y4	0,776		Valid
	Y5	0,829		Valid
	Y6	0,766		Valid

From the results of the validity test, as shown in Table 6, all the r-count values for the questionnaire items > r-table (0,1736), which indicates that all the questionnaire items are valid.

4.3 Reliability Test

The results of the reliability test using SPSS 25 are as follows:

Table 4. The Result of Reliability Test (Source: primary data processed using SPSS 25)

Variable	N of Item	Cronbach's Alpha	Alpha	Result
Content Instagram (X)	6	0,903	0,6	Highly Reliable
Customer Feedback (Z)	6	0,858		Highly Reliable
Brand Awareness (Y)	6	0,889		Highly Reliable

Based on the results of the reliability test, it was found that all variables have a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.8, indicating that all the question variables are very reliable.

4.4 F-Test

The validity test was conducted using SPSS 25 software, but first, the f-table value was determined from:

$$(df1) = k - 1, (df2) = n - k$$

$$(df1) = 3 - 1, (df2) = 128 - 3$$

$$(df1) = 2, (df2) = 125$$

$$F\ table_{(0.05,2,125)} = 3.07$$

The results of the F-test using SPSS 25 software are as follows:

Table 5. F-Test for Customer Feedback (Z) (Source: primary data processed using SPSS 25)

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	10850514,31	1	10850514,31	158,84	,000 ^b
Residual	8606673,18	126	68306,93		
Total	19457187,50	127			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Feedback					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Content					

Based on Table 4, the significance value (0.000) < alpha (0.05) and the F-value (158.849) > F-table (3.07), indicating that Instagram Content (X) influences Customer Feedback (Z). In other words, the model used is appropriate and valid.

Table 6. F-Test for Brand Awareness (Y) (Source: primary data processed using SPSS 25)

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	10749570,189	2	5374785,094	81,935	,000 ^b
Residual	8199726,686	125	65597,813		
Total	18949296,875	127			
a. Dependent Variable: Brand Awareness					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Feedback, Content					

Based on Table 5, the significance value (0.000) < alpha (0.05) and the F-value (81.935) > F-table (3.07), indicating that Instagram content (X) and customer feedback (Z) influences Brand Awareness (Y). In other words, the model used is appropriate and valid.

4.5 Partial T-Test

The validity test was conducted using SPSS 25 software. Before proceeding, the t-table value was determined using the following formula:

$$df = n - 2$$

$$df = 128 - 2 = 126$$

$$t_{tabel(0,05,125)} = 1.979$$

4.5.1 The influence of instagram content (X) on customer feedback (Z)

The T-test results of Instagram Content (X) on Customer Feedback (Z) using SPSS 25 software are as follows:

Table 7. Results of the T-test for Instagram Content (X)

on Customer Feedback (Z) (Source: primary data processed using SPSS 25)

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	522,641	134,710		3,880	0,000
Content	0,740	0,059	0,747	12,604	0,000
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Feedback					

Based on the output in Table 6, it can be concluded that t-value (12.604) > t-table (1.979) indicates that there is an effect of Instagram Content (X) on Customer Feedback (Z). The regression equation obtained is as follows:

$$Z = \alpha + \beta X + \epsilon$$

$$Z = 522.641 + 0.740X + \epsilon$$

The constant value from the unstandardized coefficients is 522.641, which means that if there is no Instagram Content (X), the value of Customer Feedback (Z) will be 522.641. The regression coefficient is 0.740, which means that for every increase of 1 in Instagram Content (X), Customer Feedback (Z) will increase by 0.740. Since the coefficient is positive, it indicates that the higher the quality of Instagram Content (X), the more positively it will affect Customer Feedback (Z).

4.5.2 The influence of customer feedback (Z) on brand awareness (Y)

The results of the T-test for Customer Feedback (Z) against Brand Awareness (Y) using SPSS 25 software are as follows:

Table 8. Result of the T-Test for Customer Feedback (Z) on Brand Awareness (Y) (Source: primary data processed using SPSS 25)

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	790,292	140,386		5,629	0,000
Customer Feedback	0,689	0,063	0,698	10,939	0,000
a. Dependent Variable: Brand Awareness					

Based on the output in Table 8, it can be concluded that the t-value (10.939) is greater than the t-table value (1.979), indicating a significant effect of Customer Feedback (Z) on Brand Awareness (Y). The following regression equation was obtained:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + \varepsilon$$

$$Y = 790.292 + 0.689X + \varepsilon$$

The constant value from the unstandardized coefficients is 790.292, meaning that if there is no Customer Feedback (Z), the value of Brand Awareness (Y) will be 790.292. The regression coefficient value is 0.689, meaning that for every increase of 1 in Customer Feedback (Z), Brand Awareness (Y) will increase by 0.689. Since the coefficient value is positive, it can be that the better the Customer Feedback (Z), the more positively it will influence Brand Awareness (Y).

4.5.3 The Influence of content instagram (X) on brand awareness (Y) through customer feedback (Z)

The path analysis method can be used to test the intervening variable. Below are the results of data processing using IBM SPSS to test the intervening variable with path analysis and the Sobel test. The influence of Instagram Content (X) through Customer Feedback (Z) on Brand Awareness (Y) was tested using path analysis, and the following output was obtained:

Table 9. Summary of Regression Coefficients Test (Source: primary data processed using SPSS 25)

Variable	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Sig	Result
X → Z	0.059	0.747	0.000	Significant
X → Y	0.061	0.710	0.000	Significant
Z → Y	0.063	0.698	0.000	Significant

Based on Table 9, the direct influence of X → Z is 0.747 and significant. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of X → Z → Y is obtained by multiplying the effects between X → Z and Z → Y which results in 0.747 × 0.698 = 0.5214. The total effect is 0.710 + (0.747 × 0.698) = 1.2314 [33].

Next, a mediation test is conducted using the Sobel test as follows:

$$sab = \sqrt{b^2sa^2 + a^2sb^2 + sa^2sb^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{(0.698^2 \times 0.059^2) + (0.747^2 \times 0.063^2) + (0.059^2 \times 0.063^2)}$$

$$= \sqrt{(0.00169) + (0.00221) + (0.00001)}$$

$$= \sqrt{0,00391}$$

$$= 0,06252$$

To test the significance of the indirect effect, the t-value of the coefficient ab needs to be calculated using the formula:

$$t = \frac{ab}{sab}$$

$$t = \frac{(0.747 \times 0.698)}{0.06252}$$

$$t = 8.33982$$

The calculated t-value is 8.33982. Since the t-value (8.33982) is greater than the t-table value (1.979), it can be concluded that Content Instagram (X) through Customer Feedback (Z) has a positive and significant effect on Brand Awareness (Y). This result can further be confirmed using the Sobel calculator <https://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>, where the output will provide additional verification for the significance of the indirect effect.:

Input:	Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a 0.747	Sobel test: 8.33775367	0.06253555	0
b 0.698	Aroian test: 8.32306436	0.06264592	0
s _a 0.059	Goodman test: 8.35252103	0.06242499	0
s _b 0.063	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 6. Output Calculator Sobel (Source: primary data processed using quantpsy.org)

The result from the Sobel calculator, as shown in Figure 6, indicates that the calculated t-value (8.33775367) is greater than the t-table value (1.979). Therefore, it can be concluded that Content on Instagram (X) through Customer Feedback (Z) has a positive and significant effect on Brand Awareness (Y).

4.6 Discussion

This study contributes to the growing body of research on the role of Instagram in brand awareness by specifically examining how Instagram content, Instagram ads, and influencers directly and indirectly impact brand awareness through customer feedback. While prior studies, such as [38], have established the general effectiveness of Instagram as a branding tool, this research extends the discussion by incorporating customer engagement as a mediating factor. Additionally, unlike [39], who focused on consumer perceptions of Instagram ads, this study examines how different Instagram marketing elements interact to enhance brand awareness in the context of Miniso X Samono Kudus.

This research differs from previous studies in several ways. First, it integrates multiple Instagram marketing strategies—Instagram ads, influencers, and content formats—whereas studies like [40] and [41] primarily focused on a single element, such as ads or influencer marketing. By doing so, this study provides a more comprehensive

understanding of how Instagram marketing can drive brand awareness. Second, while previous research often examined Instagram's impact on brand awareness in broader industries, such as iDeviceStoreJogja [38] and CV Media Computindo [40], this study provides a more focused analysis on Miniso X Samono Kudus, offering practical insights for retail brands with specific target audiences.

Another key contribution of this study is its emphasis on customer feedback as a mediating variable. While past research, such as [38], primarily analyzed the direct impact of Instagram usage on brand awareness, they did not consider customer engagement as an intermediary factor. This study highlights that active audience interaction and sentiment play a crucial role in shaping brand perception, reinforcing the argument that brands must not only create engaging content but also actively respond to customer feedback to strengthen brand awareness.

Despite its contributions, this study has certain limitations. Unlike [38], who utilized qualitative methods with interviews and observations, this research relied solely on quantitative survey data, which may not fully capture consumer motivations. Additionally, the use of incidental sampling may limit the generalizability of findings compared to studies employing probability sampling. Lastly, while this study successfully identifies the impact of Instagram marketing on brand awareness, it does not measure long-term brand equity, which could be explored in future research.

By addressing these gaps, this study enhances the understanding of Instagram marketing strategies and provides actionable insights for brands like Miniso X Samono Kudus seeking to optimize their digital branding efforts. Furthermore, since this study focuses on a brand within Indonesia's lifestyle and home appliances sector, the findings may not be entirely generalizable to other brands within the same sector or across different industries. Variations in consumer behavior, market dynamics, and cultural influences suggest that applying the same variables to brands in different industries or countries could yield different results. Future research could explore cross-industry and cross-country comparisons to better understand the adaptability of these Instagram marketing strategies in diverse market contexts.

5. CONCLUSION

This study reinforces the critical role of Instagram content, Instagram ads, and influencers in

building brand awareness, demonstrating both direct and indirect effects through customer feedback. The findings confirm that engaging and interactive content not only enhances brand recognition but also encourages consumer interaction, which in turn strengthens brand awareness. This emphasizes the need for brands to develop high-quality visuals, targeted Instagram ads, influencer collaborations, and creative storytelling strategies to maintain audience engagement and loyalty.

Unlike previous studies that primarily focused on Instagram usage frequency [38] or promotional effectiveness [39]; [40], this research highlights customer feedback as a crucial mediating factor. The results indicate that brands that actively listen to and incorporate consumer feedback into their Instagram marketing strategies can significantly improve their brand perception and market positioning. This aligns with findings from [41], who emphasized the role of influencer engagement in enhancing brand awareness.

These insights provide valuable recommendations for brands like Miniso X Samono Kudus, suggesting that continuous innovation in Instagram content, strategic ad placements, and active engagement with customer responses can drive stronger brand awareness. However, as this study focuses on a single brand in Indonesia's lifestyle and home appliances sector, findings may vary when applied to different industries, geographical context, or social media platforms. Future research could explore additional mediators, such as algorithmic content optimization, the long-term impact of influencer partnerships, or the role of AI-driven consumer sentiment analysis, to gain deeper insights into the evolving digital branding landscape.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS (CREDIT STATEMENT)

Aisya Putri Zanuaziqi:

Conceptualization, Data Collection, Data Analysis & Interpretation, Writing Original Draft, Paper Review, Journal Selection, Submission, Writing - Review and Editing, Resubmission. **Irmawan Rahyadi:** Paper Evaluation, Review of Revision, Evaluation of Revised Manuscript. **Anis Faiqoh Nurullita:** Journal Selection, Paper Review, Submission, Writing - Review and Editing, Resubmission. **Divia Indira Arifin:** Journal Selection, Paper Review, Submission, Writing - Review and Editing, Resubmission.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Meltwater, "Top Social Media Platforms in Indonesia," 24 April 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.meltwater.com/en/blog/social-media-statistics-indonesia>.
- [2] I. P. P. Supriyadi, "Pengaruh Influencer Instagram dan Intensitas Penggunaan Media Sosial," in *FRIMA (Festival Riset Ilmiah Manajemen & Akuntansi)*, Bandung, 2020.
- [3] C. M. Annur, "Indonesia Jadi Negara dengan Pengguna Instagram Terbanyak ke-4 di Dunia," 28 November 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2023/11/28/indonesia-jadi-negara-dengan-pengguna-instagram-terbanyak-ke-4-di-dunia>.
- [4] Asosiasi Penyelenggara Jasa Internet Indonesia (APJII), "APJII Jumlah Pengguna Internet Indonesia Tembus 221 Juta Orang," 7 February 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://apjii.or.id/berita/d/apjii-jumlah-pengguna-internet-indonesia-tembus-221-juta-orang#:~:text=Asosiasi%20Penyelenggara%20Jasa%20Internet%20Indonesia%20\(APJII\)%20mengumumkan%20jumlah%20pengguna%20internet,jawa%20penduduk%20Indonesia%20tahun%202023..](https://apjii.or.id/berita/d/apjii-jumlah-pengguna-internet-indonesia-tembus-221-juta-orang#:~:text=Asosiasi%20Penyelenggara%20Jasa%20Internet%20Indonesia%20(APJII)%20mengumumkan%20jumlah%20pengguna%20internet,jawa%20penduduk%20Indonesia%20tahun%202023..)
- [5] F. P. Simbolon, R. A. Nurcholifa and M. Safarina, "The Influence of Using Instagram as a Promotional Media in Building Brand Awareness and Its Impact on Purchase Decision of Bulog Products in Shopee," *Binus Business Review*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 57-66, 2022.
- [6] Kontan.co.id, "Pertumbuhan Bisnis Ritel Kuartal III-2024 Cukup Menantang, Ini Penyebabnya," 30 June 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://industri.kontan.co.id/news/pertumbuhan-bisnis-ritel-kuartal-iii-2024-cukup-menantang-ini-penyebabnya>.
- [7] I. Ajzen, "Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes," *Elsevier*, pp. Pages 179-211, December 1991.
- [8] M. Fishbein and I. Ajzen, *Belief, Attitude, Intention, and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1975.
- [9] I. Ajzen, *Attitudes, Personality, and Behavior* (2nd ed.), New York: Open University Press, 2005.
- [10] L. Festinger, *Cognitive Dissonance*, Scientific American, 1962.
- [11] E. Harmon-Jones and J. Mills, "An introduction to cognitive dissonance theory and an overview of current perspectives on the theory.," *ReseqarchGate*, 2018.
- [12] P. Pham and B. Gammoh, "Characteristics of social-media marketing strategy and customer-based brand equity outcomes: A conceptual model," *ResearchGate*, pp. 321-337, 2015.
- [13] F. Rangkuti, *Measuring Customer Satisfaction*, Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2002.
- [14] İ. H. Efindioğlu and Y. Durmaz, "The Impact of Perceptions of Social Media Advertisements on Advertising Value, Brand Awareness and Brand Associations: Research on Generation Y Instagram Users," *Transnational Marketing Journal*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 251-275, 2022.
- [15] R. Pappu, P. G. Quester and R. W. Cooksey, "Consumer-based brand equity and country-of-origin relationships: Some empirical evidence," *European Journal of Marketing*, vol. 40, no. 5/6, pp. 696-717, 2006.
- [16] K. Gwinner, "A model of image creation and image transfer in event sponsorship," *International Marketing Review*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 145-158, 1997.
- [17] D. A. Aaker, "The Value of Brand Equity," *Journal of Business Strategy*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 27-32, 1992.
- [18] N. B. E. Danah M Boyd, "Social Network Sites: Definition, History and Scholarship," *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 2008.
- [19] S. Kingsnorth, *Digital marketing strategy: An integrated approach to online marketing*, London: Kogan Page Limited, 2016.
- [20] Y. S. R. Lubis, "Analisis Konten Instagram @Batampromotion dalam Membangun Citra Pariwisata Kota Batam," *UPB REPO*, 2023.
- [21] R. Nurmuhhammad and I. N. A. Pamungkas, "THE INFLUENCE OF INSTAGRAM CONTENT TO THE CONSUMER ATTITUDE OF MOBILE GAME PT. AGATE INTERNATIONAL," *e-*

- Proceeding of Management : Vol.7, No.1 April 2020*, pp. 1752-1767, 2020.
- [22] M. Solomon, G. Marshall and E. Stuart, *Marketing: Real People, Real Choices*, 11th edition, Pearson, 2021.
- [23] G. Indriani, A. Syantoso and A. Purnomo, "PENGARUH CUSTOMER FEEDBACK PADA TOKOPEDIA SALAM TERHADAP," *Unsika*, 2024.
- [24] M. Haverila and E. Naumann, "Customer Complaint Behavior And Satisfaction In A B2b Context: A Longitudinal Analysis," *Vedatya*, no. 2, 2010.
- [25] D. A. Aaker, *Brand Portfolio Strategy: Creating Relevance, Differentiation, Energy, Leverage, and Clarity*, New York: Free Press, 2020.
- [26] Humas Indonesia, "Kenali 4 Tingkatan "Brand Awareness"," 19 January 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.humasindonesia.id/berita/kenali-4-tingkatan-brand-awareness--1795>.
- [27] D. A. Aaker, *Strategic Market Management*, New York: John Wiley and Sons, Inc, 2001.
- [28] M. A. Widiyanto, *STATISTIKA TERAPAN Konsep & Aplikasi SPSS/LISREL dalam Penelitian Pendidikan, Psikologi & Ilmu Sosial Lainnya*, Jakarta: PT Elex Media Komputindo, 2013.
- [29] A. Ferdinand, "Structural Equation Modelling Dalam Penelitian Manajemen"., Semarang: Badan Penerbit UNDIP Semarang, 2002.
- [30] D. A. N. N. Dewi, "Modul Uji Validitas dan Reliabilitas," *ResearchGate*, 2018.
- [31] A. Ahdika, "Improvement of Quality, Interest, Critical, and Analytical Thinking Ability of Student through the Application of Research Based Learning (RBL) in Introduction to Stochastic Processes Subject," *ResearchGate*, pp. 167-190, 2017.
- [32] U. Sekaran and R. Bougie, *Research Methods for Business*, New York: John Wiley & Sons Inc, 2016.
- [33] I. Ghozali, *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 25*, Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro, 2018.
- [34] S. Raharjo, "Panduan Lengkap Uji Analisis Regresi Linear Sederhana dengan SPSS," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.spssindonesia.com/2017/03/uji-analisis-regresi-linear-sederhana.html>.
- [35] S. Abu-Bader and T. V. Jones, "Statistical Mediation Analysis Using the Sobel Test and Hayes SPSS Process Macro," *International Journal of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods*, pp. 42-61, 2021.
- [36] K. J. Preacher and G. J. Leonardelli, "Calculation for the Sobel Test," 2010-2024. [Online]. Available: <https://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>.
- [37] J. Adnan and K. , "Determinant of Auditor Ability to Detect Fraud with Professional Scepticism as A Mediator Variable," *Determinant of Auditor Ability to Detect Fraud with Professional Scepticism as A Mediator Variable. Accounting Analysis Journal*, pp. 313-325, 2017.
- [38] C. A. Perdana and D. Dimiyati, "The role of instagram in building brand awareness," *Enrichment: Journal of Management*, pp. 1654-1664, 2023.
- [39] İ. H. Efendioğlu and Y. Durmaz, "The Impact of Perceptions of Social Media Advertisements on Advertising Value, Brand Awareness and Brand Associations: Research on Generation Y Instagram Users," *Transnational Marketing Journal*, 2022.
- [40] N. Khotimah and D. Rachmawati, "Kalahkan China, Indonesia Jadi Rumah Bagi Miniso Land Terbesar di Dunia," 01 September 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.suara.com/lifestyle/2024/09/01/090857/kalahkan-china-indonesia-jadi-rumah-bagi-miniso-land-terbesar-di-dunia>.
- [41] S. R. Jovanovska and I. B. Gavrilova, "Increasing Customers' Brand Awareness With Influencer Marketing: A Focus On Instagram," *International Scietific Conference on Economic and Social Development*, 2021.